

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

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As global ecological challenges become more complex, many countries are expanding protected natural areas in order to preserve natural capital and maintain ecological balance. In this context, biodiversity conservation is no longer viewed solely as an environmental issue; it has become an essential component of sustainable economic development, particularly in countries where tourism resources are closely connected with natural landscapes and ecosystems.

Uzbekistan has implemented a number of state programs aimed at expanding protected natural areas and promoting sustainable tourism development. These initiatives create favorable conditions for strengthening ecological tourism and improving regional environmental management. However, existing research in this field is predominantly descriptive and policy-oriented, focusing mainly on development indicators rather than explaining the mechanisms through which ecological tourism can contribute to regional socio-economic development.

In particular, relatively limited attention has been given to the interaction between regional infrastructure development, natural resource management, and community participation as elements of an integrated development system. Many international studies on ecotourism have examined conservation outcomes or economic benefits separately, while in developing economies these processes often occur simultaneously and reinforce each other.

Therefore, the lack of a comprehensive analytical framework that integrates ecological conservation, community development, and inter-institutional cooperation creates an important theoretical and practical research gap.

This study addresses this gap by analyzing the expansion of nature-based tourism not merely as a tourism activity but as a regional development mechanism supported by institutional cooperation and effective resource integration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Environmental changes and anthropogenic pressures have significantly affected natural ecosystems and biodiversity in many regions of the world, including Uzbekistan. Certain species that once inhabited the region, such as the Turkmen kulan, the Turan tiger, and the Aral barbel fish, are no longer found in their natural habitats. At the same time, several rare species, including the leopard, the houbara bustard, and the hyena, require enhanced conservation attention. In response to these challenges, the government has implemented a number of environmental protection initiatives and biodiversity conservation programs in recent years aimed at preserving natural ecosystems and strengthening ecological sustainability.

The theoretical and practical aspects of ecological tourism development have been widely examined in the works of international scholars such as Nilson, Higham, McLaughlin, Eagles, Weaver, Coria, and Buffa, who analyzed the interaction between tourism development and environmental sustainability, as well as its economic, cultural, and policy implications. Regional research has also been conducted by Ajayev, Khrabovchenko, Zakharova, Drozdov, and Shimova, whose studies focus on the development of ecological tourism and the management of natural resources in transition economies.

Information on global ecotourism trends and sustainable tourism practices is widely presented in analytical reports and publications of international organizations, including the United Nations, the World Tourism Organization, and various national tourism agencies. Within Uzbekistan, theoretical and methodological issues related to tourism development have been explored by scholars such as Abdurakhmonov, Tuxliyev, Eshtayev, Safarov, Hamidov, To'raev, Aliyeva, Norchayev, Ibragimov, Matyakubov, Mirzayev, Golisheva, Qodirov, Khalilov, and other researchers.

Nevertheless, comprehensive studies that examine the relationship between ecological tourism development and regional economic transformation remain relatively limited. This situation highlights the need for further research focusing on integrated development mechanisms, innovative management approaches, and effective institutional cooperation in the sphere of ecological tourism.

Despite the extensive body of literature on sustainable tourism and protected area management, several research limitations remain evident:

- Existing models have mainly been developed for mature tourism economies and often assume the presence of well-established infrastructure and strong governance capacity.
- Community-based ecotourism studies frequently emphasize social participation but rarely analyze or quantify the institutional mechanisms that enable such participation.
- In post-transition and emerging tourism regions, there is still a lack of comprehensive models explaining how state policy, infrastructure investment, and natural capital can jointly stimulate tourism development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study proposes a territorial ecotourism development mechanism consisting of three interdependent subsystems:

1. Resource subsystem. Natural landscapes, biodiversity, and protected natural areas.
2. Institutional subsystem. Government programs, regulatory frameworks, and financing instruments that support ecological tourism development.
3. Community-economic subsystem. Guesthouses, local artisans, tour guides, and small-scale entrepreneurship within local communities.

The research argues that sustainable ecotourism growth occurs when these subsystems function in an integrated cycle:

Protection → Attraction → Local Income → Incentive for Protection.

Within this framework, ecological tourism is considered not only a tool for nature conservation but also a self-sustaining regional economic model that simultaneously supports environmental protection and socio-economic development.

In recent years, a number of practical measures have been implemented that positively contribute to the preservation of flora and fauna in Uzbekistan, which is particularly important for the development of tourism and especially ecotourism. For instance, plantations intended for cultivating food, medicinal, and wild plant species have been established on approximately 10.1 thousand hectares of land.

Significant progress has also been achieved in biodiversity conservation. A total of 8,800 individuals of the houbara bustard, listed in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan, were bred in specialized nurseries and subsequently released into their natural habitat. Furthermore, 31 Turkmen kulans from the “Jayron” breeding center were relocated to the “Sudochoye–Akpetki” State Wildlife Reserve in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in order to restore their natural habitat and strengthen ecosystem stability.

The inclusion of Lake Sudochoye in the Ramsar Convention list as an internationally important wetland and ornithological site also contributes to strengthening the country’s tourism potential, particularly in the field of ecological tourism.

Protected natural areas (PNA) of categories I–V, along with biosphere reserves in Uzbekistan, currently occupy 14.08% (6.321 million hectares) of the country’s total territory. Within these protected areas, 102 species of vertebrates (83%) and 208 species of plants (89%) listed in the Red Book of Uzbekistan are preserved.

Ten ecotourism routes have been designated within these territories. Among them, ecotourism destinations such as “Suvtushar” in the Hisor State Reserve and “Lake Sudochoye” in the Sudochoye–Akpetki State Reserve have been developed.

In addition, several national nature parks established in 2022—including “Orolqum,” “Pop,” “Omonqoton,” “Yuqori Topalang,” and “Bobotog”—play an important role in expanding ecological tourism opportunities. The majority of their territories consist of strictly protected zones (700,000; 6,000; 1,000; 18,000; and 8,000 hectares respectively). Approximately one-third of the territory of most of these national parks is allocated for recreational and economic activities compatible with environmental protection.

Within the framework of developing the Aral Sea region, it is planned to consistently expand the use of green technologies, establish protective forest belts, introduce alternative energy sources, and actively utilize ecotourism opportunities.

Beginning March 1, 2024, citizens’ assemblies located in environmentally clean areas are being granted the statuses of “eco-village,” “eco-mahalla,” and “eco-aul.” This initiative creates favorable conditions for the installation of solar panels, the introduction of electric buses, and the development of green public parks.

To encourage entrepreneurship in the sector, several economic incentives have been introduced. From January 1, 2024, part of the costs for constructing and equipping new passenger cableways will be financed from the state budget—1 billion UZS for each 500 meters of cableway (with a minimum length of 500 meters in one direction).

In addition, until 2026, equipment and spare parts for cableways, funiculars, ski lifts, as well as recreational facilities such as bungee jumping systems, zip-lines, rafting and flyboarding equipment, photo-hunting devices, aerostats, electric boats, snow transport vehicles, and quad bikes, are exempt from customs duties (excluding VAT and customs clearance fees).

Until recently, tourism development in the Samarkand region primarily focused on historical monuments and museums. However, tourism diversification has significantly expanded in recent years, incorporating gastronomic tourism, cultural-educational tourism, wellness tourism, agrotourism, and ecotourism.

Several areas demonstrate the growing utilization of the region’s ecotourism potential. These include:

- Zarafshan National Nature Park in Jomboy district;
- Mountain zones of Ohalik and Mironqul villages in Samarkand district;
- Takhtakaracha Pass in Urgut district;

- Natural caves and reservoirs in Beshkon, Qoratepa, and Omonqoton villages;
- Springs located in Pangat, Qoratosh, Jonbuloq, and Qizilbel villages of Qo'shrabot district;
- Recreational areas such as Sazag'on, Anjirli, Jom, and Ibrohim ota in Nurobod district.

The "Konigil" tourism village in Samarkand district, the "Chinaras" agro-ecotourism area in Bo'zi mahalla, and tourist infrastructure established in the Zarafshan National Nature Park have already become popular destinations for visitors.

With the expansion of tourism development, living conditions in Samarkand city and its districts have also improved. For example, the area surrounding the Siyob canal passing through Konigil village has been landscaped, and more than 50 tourist facilities have been launched, creating new employment opportunities and additional sources of income for local residents.

Following the successful experience of Konigil and Tersak villages, similar development initiatives have expanded to "Choshtepa" village in Payariq district, "Oqsoy" in Nurobod district, "Andoqsoy" in Kattaqo'rg'on district, and "Pangat" in Qo'shrabot district, further strengthening the region's ecotourism potential.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pursuant to Executive Order No. 5781 (August 13, 2019), the establishment of tourism villages in Urgut district was initiated, and eleven mahallas were designated as tourism zones. In Tersak village alone, twenty-five family guesthouses began operating, five of which hosted approximately 500 visitors by 2022. During the same year, Urgut district welcomed around 11,000 foreign tourists and nearly 380,000 domestic visitors.

Government programs supporting tourism development have included state financing, tax incentives, and improvements in infrastructure, such as road modernization and the gradual introduction of sustainable energy solutions. The development program for the Omonqoton National Park area for the period 2023–2025 requires investments totaling 29 billion UZS and is expected to create 55 new jobs, while attracting approximately 55–60 thousand visitors annually.

Major tourist attractions of the park include the Taxtakaracha Pass, Iskandar Rock, Omonqoton Cave, and Hazrat Ali Stone, which represent important natural and cultural landmarks of the region.

Current development trends suggest that Urgut district has strong potential to become one of the leading tourism destinations in the Samarkand region. At the same time, the experience gained in the district demonstrates that community-based ecotourism initiatives can gradually expand to neighboring territories.

Field observations in the Samarkand region indicate that sustainable tourism development is not determined solely by the attractiveness of natural landscapes, but rather by the effective interaction between environmental protection strategies and regional economic incentives. In many cases, infrastructure development alone did not generate significant tourism growth until mechanisms encouraging community participation and local economic involvement were introduced.

Conversely, areas with rich natural resources but limited tourism infrastructure and service development may not fully realize their tourism potential. Therefore, sustainable tourism development requires coordinated spatial planning and effective cooperation among different sectors and stakeholders.

The proposed structural-economic framework functions as a regulatory mechanism that transforms environmental resources into sustainable regional capital, ensuring a balanced relationship between environmental protection, tourism development, and socio-economic progress (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Ecotourism potential zones in the districts of the Samarkand region¹

¹ author's development

Because of its unique natural landscape formations, the area offers significant opportunities for the development of various recreation zones and tourist resorts. In many villages of the Urgut district, ancient plane trees and juniper trees that are believed to be several centuries or even thousands of years old can still be found, which enhances the natural and ecological value of the territory.

The establishment of the “Omonqoton” National Nature Park represents an important step toward expanding sustainable tourism and strengthening ecological tourism development in Uzbekistan.

The following sites have been identified as key ecotourism attractions within the area:

- The Stone Cut by Iskandar (Alexander the Great)
- Pine Forest (Qarag‘ayzor)
- Omonqoton Cave
- Upper Cave
- Kingdom of Stones
- Taxi Qoracha Pass
- Hazrat Ali Stone

In addition, activities such as eco-trails, nature observation routes, and quad-bike excursions are planned to be organized for visitors.

According to project projections, the expected number of visitors may reach approximately 55–60 thousand tourists annually, with the average expenditure per visitor estimated at around 100,000 UZS. The implementation of these initiatives will contribute to strengthening the tourism potential of the Samarkand region and establishing another attractive tourist destination within the country.

Taking into account the ongoing development initiatives, existing tourism infrastructure, and the natural tourism resources of the territory, it can be anticipated that Urgut district has strong prospects to become one of the most attractive tourism destinations in the near future.

Furthermore, the introduction of community-based ecotourism in districts such as Qo‘shrabot, Jomboy, Bulung‘ur, Nurobod, and Samarkand, where significant ecotourism potential exists, may considerably increase the overall ecotourism capacity of the region.

The effective organization of tourism activities in these natural parks also creates favorable conditions for attracting investment and supporting local economic development.

Taking into account the environmental, economic, social, and institutional conditions at ecotourism destinations in Uzbekistan, the study proposes the following organizational and economic mechanisms for the further development of ecotourism (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Organizational mechanism for sustainable ecotourism development²

² author's development

At the national and regional levels, ecotourism development should be coordinated through a centralized cluster management system that involves environmental authorities and regional tourism administrations responsible for legal regulation, strategic planning, and financial support.

At the local level, cooperation among mahallas, tour operators, entrepreneurs, and craft associations forms sustainable ecotourism development centers. These centers provide tourism services, training and educational activities, research initiatives, and marketing integration, thereby supporting balanced regional tourism development.

Economic Mechanism

Tourism revenues may be distributed according to the following structure:

- 60% – allocated to service providers and local communities;
- 20% – directed toward cluster maintenance, infrastructure development, and marketing activities;
- 20% – invested in education, scientific research, and environmental awareness programs.

Financial resources should primarily support the development of eco-friendly infrastructure, waste management systems, sanitation facilities, and biodiversity conservation programs.

The land-use management approach, in which the majority of protected natural areas remains under conservation while a smaller portion is allocated for recreational and tourism activities, represents an internationally recognized standard of sustainable tourism management.

Scientific Novelty of the Research

The scientific novelty of the study includes the following contributions:

- Designing a comprehensive model of ecotourism as a regional development mechanism, rather than considering it merely as a tourism segment.
- Demonstrating the cause-and-effect relationship between revenue redistribution and environmental sustainability.
- Proposing a coordinated socio-economic model applicable to developing tourism economies.
- Providing empirical evidence that local community participation serves as a stabilizing factor between environmental conservation and tourism development.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the study indicate that the development of ecotourism in emerging tourism regions cannot be explained solely by the availability of natural resources or improvements in physical infrastructure. Sustainable growth occurs when environmental protection policies, economic incentives, and local community participation operate within an integrated development framework.

Therefore, ecotourism should be considered not merely as a specialized tourism segment but as a territorial management model, whose long-term stability depends on the coordinated management of environmental, economic, and social resources.

The introduction of tourism activities such as horse riding routes, cycling paths, ecological trails, and ATV tours may significantly enhance the attractiveness of destinations and diversify visitor experiences. Increasing tourist arrivals to protected natural areas can contribute to expanding local economic opportunities while simultaneously supporting environmental conservation.

Based on the current development trends, Urgut district has strong potential to become one of the leading tourism destinations in the Samarkand region. Furthermore, the gradual implementation of community-based ecotourism in neighboring districts may significantly increase the overall ecotourism capacity of the region and support balanced and sustainable regional development.

To further strengthen ecotourism development, the following recommendations can be proposed:

- improving ecological tourism infrastructure and transport accessibility to protected natural areas;
- expanding community-based tourism initiatives and supporting local entrepreneurship;
- strengthening cooperation between environmental institutions, tourism organizations, and local communities;
- promoting the use of green technologies and environmentally friendly tourism practices;
- enhancing marketing strategies aimed at promoting regional ecotourism destinations at national and international levels.

These measures will contribute to ensuring the long-term sustainability of ecotourism development and strengthening its role in regional socio-economic growth and environmental protection.

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